

Breast Cancer Prediction Using CNN

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Abstract. Globally, breast cancer ranks as the second most common cause of cancer-related deaths among women. However, if caught early enough, it's also one of the most curable cancers. Screening for breast cancer with histopathology images has been widely used. One of the most prevalent types of cancer in women is breast cancer, which develops in the breast cells. Early detection of cancer followed by the proper treatment can reduce the risk of deaths. This paper investigates the proposed system that uses convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures to automatically detect breast cancer, comparing the results with those from machine learning (ML) algorithms. CNN is useful for this kind of detection. Pre-trained networks are used in CNN design, which will increase accuracy metrics. By analysing hostile ductal carcinoma tissue zones in whole slide images (WSIs), a convolutional neural network (CNN) method is proposed in this study to improve the automatic identification of breast cancer.

Keywords: CNN, Breast Cancer, Pooling Matrix, Convolutional matrix

1 Introduction

One of the most prevalent types of cancer in women is breast cancer, which develops in the breast cells. After lung cancer, breast cancer is a disease that can kill a woman's life. Breast cancer is classified into different categories based on how the cell appears under a microscope. Cancer develops when cells from the aberrant body begin to divide, come into contact with normal cells, and transform them into malignant cells. In the world, breast cancer is the most common and dangerous disease. Breast cancer is classified as either non-invasive or invasive. Malignant and carcinogenic, invasive substances spread to other organs. Non-invasive is in its original organ and is precancerous. It finally progresses to become aggressive breast cancer. The glands and milk ducts that convey milk are the parts of the body where breast cancer is found.

Breast cancer frequently metastasized to other organs, turning them aggressive. Additionally, it spreads to other organs via the bloodstream. There are numerous varieties of breast cancer, and their growth rates vary as well. The WHO reports that 627,000 women lost their lives to breast cancer in 2018. The primary issue that affects people worldwide but is most prevalent in the United States of America is breast cancer. Breast cancer comes in four different forms. The first kind of cancer is called Ductal Carcinoma in Situ, which is pre-stage breast cancer that is discovered in the covering of the breast milk ducts. The most common kind

of breast cancer, accounting for 70–80% of cases, is the second kind. The third type of breast cancer is called inflammatory breast cancer, which develops violently and fast. Inflammatory breast cancer cells pierce the breast's surface and lymph veins. Metastatic breast cancer is the fourth form of breast cancer, meaning that it has spread to other bodily parts. Numerous diagnostic procedures, including biopsy, ultrasound, MRI, mammography, and histopathology pictures, produced the images needed for classification. Using an X-ray, a mammography is performed to detect breast cancer. If any unusual results are discovered during a mammography screening, the physician is notified to test the tissues. Following a mammography, an ultrasound is performed. When the doctor finds a questionable location in your breast, they will request an ultrasound. If the results of the symptomatic examination don't convince the doctor, the breast MRI is preferred. It portrays the image and perspective of your sickness. The primary diagnostic method for determining whether a suspected area is carcinogenic is a biopsy.

Instruments have been developed to create and enhance image processing since images have inherent challenges such as low contrast, noise, and lack of visual appreciation. These days, the fastest growing segments of the healthcare business are convolutional neural networks (CNNs), machine learning (ML), and artificial intelligence (AI). AI and ML are used in research that addresses and advances technological solutions to tackle challenging problems by lowering the need for human intelligence.

A significant factor in the classification of breast cancer is machine learning. Many of the diagnosis procedures that were previously addressed include the provision of photographs. Machine learning is employed for the classification of certain diagnostic image types. AI includes machine learning as a subfield. A lot of developers utilise machine learning to improve performance and retrain existing models. The linear data is processed using machine learning. Machine learning performs better when the data is tiny; yet, it is not as effective when the data is vast. The model is trained using three primary forms of machine learning. With the supervisor's assistance and using known data, supervised machine learning operates. Unsupervised machine learning is taken without any supervision. A branch of machine learning is called deep learning. Deep learning is an unsupervised approach that utilizes data to learn. Both unstructured and unlabelled data are possible. A deep neural network is defined as one that has more than two hidden layers. In essence, the input layer is the first layer, and the output layer is the second. With more layers than a neural network, the intermediate layer is known as the hidden layer. The layer known as neurons is contained in the node. The key distinction between deep learning and machine learning is that the latter is less far from its objective. A convolution neural network is utilized to classify the breast cancer dataset.

Within the machine learning family, deep learning (DL) relies on artificial neural networks. The fields of computer vision, audio recognition, speech recognition, social network filtering, natural language processing, machine translation, drug design, bioinformatics, medical image analysis, materials scrutiny, histopathological diagnosis, and board game programmes are commonly served by DL architectures like DNN (deep neural networks), RNN (recurrent neural networks). Within the machine learning family, deep learning (DL) relies on artificial neural networks. The fields of computer vision, audio recognition, speech recognition, social network filtering, natural language processing, machine translation, drug design, bioinformatics, medical image analysis, materials scrutiny, histopathological diagnosis, and board game programmes are commonly served by DL architectures like DNN (deep neural networks), RNN (recurrent neural

networks), DBN (deep belief networks), and CNN. These new technologies, in particular DL algorithms, can be used to increase the diagnostic accuracy and efficiency of cancer detection.

2 Literature Review

The potential that CNN offers for studying medical imaging is not limited to using deep CNN to extract imaging features. In fact, using CNN for artificial image rendering is a second area that can help medical research. In a study that use MF-CNN (multifaceted fused-CNN) and a hybrid descriptor, Wahab and Khan [1] found that suitable colour and textural qualities are established to help mitotic countbased selection of ROIs at reduced resolution. MF-CNN identifies dynamic patterns by identifying many aspects of the input image. In order to train a classifier that assigns WSIs scores, it incorporates mitoses, extracts, and handcrafted features from ROIs. The global image texture is used to create a hybrid descriptor. Unimaginable possibilities are emerging on CNNs in domains where successful feature development is a laborious task for domain specialists. Gravina et al. [2] pointed out that because "medical images are more exceptional than normal images," the naive application of CNNs might not work. It has been demonstrated that mammographic lesion segmentation is a useful source of information because it can be used to precisely localise lesions as well as extract structures linked to shape.

Tsochatzidis et al. [3] conducted an experiment to test the accuracy of CNN-based mammograms in the diagnosis of breast cancer. They demonstrate that performance assessment in diagnosis is done on two datasets of mammographic mass, such as DDSM-400 and CBISDDSM, with differences in the corresponding segmentation maps of ground truth.

Malathi et al. [4] used a computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) system for mammography to enable the early detection, assessment, and management of breast cancer. They talked about using deep learning of the CNN to investigate a breast CAD architecture centred on characteristic fusion. The random forest algorithm (RFA) outperforms the CNN classifier in terms of precision and error rate (95.65%), according to the results. The deep belief network is used to investigate any abnormalities in the representations of the breast (DBN). The provided work practices initiate contour segmentation in order to identify the abnormal picture, and the DBN may order it.

According to Desai and Shah [5], in order to determine whether network performs better than the other, a thorough comparison of each network's architecture and operation is done. Then, an analysis is done based on how accurately each network diagnoses and classifies breast cancer. CNN is reported to have somewhat higher precision than MLP for the detection and identification of breast cancer. CNNs were employed by Wahab and Khan [1] in earlier studies to look at the automated identification of IDC-type breast cancer. To detect the same, a number of academics employed ML-based automatic detection algorithms. The goal is to reduce the errors discovered throughout the diagnosis process by obtaining accurate results. Using the provided dataset, the study by Abdelhafiz et al. [6] similarly found that the augmentation strategy was successful in automatically identifying this cancer. In order recognise images of mitosis in breast histology, another researcher [7] used deep max pooling CNNs. The networks were able to arrange the images depending on pixel.

Murtaza et al. [8] investigated and automatically identified IDC tissue zones using a DL technique. Hossain [9] introduced context-aware stacked CNNs to classify

breast WSIs into simple, DCIS (ductal carcinoma in situ), and IDC (invasive ductal cancer) categories. The system demonstrated its potential for regular diagnostics by obtaining

an area beneath the curve of 0.962 for the classification of malignant and nonmalignant slides and 81.3% three-class accuracy for WSI classification.

Alhamid et al.'s [10] and Qian et al.'s [11] research also provided some methods for identifying them. Their findings of their experiment demonstrated that the phase and magnitude of the shearlet coefficients could improve the generalizability and accuracy of detection AI and CNN have both been suggested for image detection and healthcare monitoring in a number of earlier studies [6,12,13, 14]. However, the accuracy percentage is too low for a medical side solution, which is roughly 60% for all class identification, 75% for only bulk class, and 100% for only calcification [15]. To get a better outcome, the accuracy of all arguments—aside from the sole calcification argument—and mass only arguments can be further improved [16]. Many techniques for identifying breast cancer have been developed recently, and the effectiveness of computer-aided detection has been confirmed using data from the UCI machine learning repository. The bigLVQ approach, the optimised learning vector quantization (LVQ) method, and the artificial immune system identified breast cancer with rates of 96.7%, 96.8%, and 97.2%, respectively [24]. Using a 10-fold cross, it was discovered that the decision tree technique with C4.5 achieved a 94.74% accuracy rate in classification [25]. Supervisory control fuzzy clustering produced an accuracy rate of 95.57%, while a neurofuzzy classifier produced a 95.06% accuracy rate [26]. The accuracy of three classifiers—multi-layer perceptron (MLP), naïve Bayes (NB), and decision tree—in classifying breast cancer using the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (WBC) dataset was examined. It was discovered that a fusion classifier composed of the MLP and J48 classifier performed better [19]. Breast cancer categorization using RIAC yielded a 96% recognition rate, while least square support vector machines (LSSVM) produced a 98.53% recognition rate [20]. The results were compared in terms of accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity, and it was shown that the robustness of LSSVM was the reason for its high accuracy rate. Through independent component analysis, the feature reduction-based breast cancer decision system was investigated. The radial basis neural network accuracy was raised to 90.49 by the verified single dimension feature [22]. Pictures of breast cancer have textural information that may have distinguishing characteristics. In order to distinguish between normal and aberrant pixels in mammograms, the texture properties of the Laws were extracted. Using texture energy obtained from mammograms, a wavelet network based on particle swarm optimisation (PSO) was used to detect anomalies related to breast cancer. It achieved 93.671%, 92.105%, and 94.167% accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity, respectively [23]. Utilising fused deep features, morphological characteristics, texture features, and density features, an extreme learning machine classifier identified the benign and malignant breast masses with an 86.50% detection rate. Although a plethora of algorithms and methods have been developed for more investigation is needed to improve the accuracy of breast cancer picture classification, thereby saving more lives. CNNs enable a reduction in the amount of field knowledge required for classification system design. As a result, the dataset utilised has less of an impact on the approaches' performance, and similar network topologies can produce good results on a variety of challenges.

As fact, Spanhol et al. [28] classified H&E breast tissue biopsy samples as benign and malignant tumours using different magnifications, utilising a CNN architecture inspired by the Imagenet network [29]. In order to train the CNN, 32×32 and 64×64 pixel

patches were taken from the original images. Combining the patch probabilities with sum, product, or maximum rules yielded the final categorization. We looked at two different patch extraction techniques: random extraction and sliding window. By reducing the size of the input in later layers, the extraction of patches made it possible to simplify the model and lower its complexity. Higher magnifications caused the authors to report a drop in accuracy, which may indicate that their CNN architecture is unable to extract pertinent characteristics at higher magnifications. In supervised learning, each sample must have data with known labels since the CNN is trained on labelled data. This indicates that the data must be organised, meaning that every input sample—such as an image—must have a matching label—such as a class or category. Supervised learning techniques make it difficult to train a CNN on unstructured or label-free data. Data without a predetermined structure or format, such as unstructured text, audio, or video data, is referred to as such. Furthermore, CNNs are specifically made for applications where the input data has a spatial structure, such as segmentation, object identification, and image classification (e.g., pixels in an image). CNNs may not be appropriate for processing unstructured data without extra preprocessing or specialized designs, despite their superiority in learning hierarchical representations from structured data, such as photographs. There may be better machine learning or deep learning techniques for tasks requiring unstructured or unlabeled data. For instance, approaches like natural language processing (NLP) for text data or unsupervised learning, where the model learns patterns and structures from unlabeled data, can be used. Typically, supervised learning frameworks are used to train CNNs. Using labelled training data, the model learns to map inputs to outputs. The model finds it challenging to acquire meaningful representations or provide precise predictions in the absence of labels. It is difficult for the model to train efficiently without labels since there is no clear goal for it to minimize the loss. It is difficult to evaluate the model's accuracy or generalization performance in the absence of labels. Without supervision, though, there's no direction on what characteristics or patterns are pertinent to the current task, which could result in less-than-ideal representations.

3 Methodology

3.1 Different Methods and Their Limitation

There are few methods to predict breast cancer. In Table 1 some of the methodologies and their limitation have been shown

Random Forest Algorithm	Because Random Forest models comprise multiple decision trees, it is challenging to understand the model as a whole. This lack of openness can be a serious disadvantage in medical settings where it's imperative to comprehend the logic underlying forecasts.
Logistic Regression	Logistic Regression is a comparatively simple model. It might not fully reflect the intricacy of histopathological images, particularly in cases where spatial relationships play a critical role in accurate categorization or when characteristics are very diverse. As a result, in jobs requiring fine-grained analysis of tissue architecture, logistic regression may perform worse than more complex models.
Support Vector Machine	SVMs may find it difficult to learn from unbalanced data, which could result in reduced performance and biased classification results, especially for the minority class. Images from histopathology can provide spatial information about the distribution and arrangement of cells and tissue structures, which is essential for a precise diagnosis. SVMs may not fully take advantage of spatial linkages because they normally work with feature vectors that are taken from images.
K-Nearest Neighbor	Histopathology images are typically represented by high-dimensional feature vectors, where each pixel or region is a feature. The concept known as the "curse of dimensionality" states that in high-dimensional spaces, the relevance of the distance between data points decreases. The decreasing reliability of the proximity notion may jeopardize KNN's accuracy in high dimensional histopathology image processing. Noise abnormalities or outliers in histopathological photos can greatly impact the similarity calculations between data points, resulting in inaccurate predictions.

3.2 Proposed Method:

Breast cancer detection using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) involves leveraging deep learning techniques to identify and classify breast cancer from medical imaging data, such as mammograms, ultrasound images, or histopathological images. Here's the steps of our proposed method

□ Data Collection and Preprocessing

These datasets contain mammogram images, histopathological images, or ultrasound images of breast tissues. All the images will be resized to a

consistent size, typically 224x224 pixels, suitable for the CNN model input. Techniques like rotation, flipping, zooming, and shifting will be applied to increase the diversity of the training data and reduce overfitting.

□ Data Splitting

Usually, 70-80% of the data is used for training the model. About 10-20% of the data is used to validate the model during training. The remaining data is used to test the final model performance.

3.3 Model Architecture

- Input Layer: Accepts the pre-processed images.
- Convolutional Layers: Extract features using various filters to create feature maps.
- ReLU Activation: Apply a Rectified Linear Unit activation function to introduce non-linearity.
- Pooling Layers: Reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps using techniques like max pooling.
- Fully Connected Layers: Flatten the output from the convolutional layers and connect to one or more dense layers.
- Output Layer: Typically, a softmax activation function for multi-class classification (benign, malignant) or a sigmoid activation function for binary classification.

4 Result and Analysis:

We have tested this Convolutional model in different approach. Here is some tested result in the table below, where different hyper parameter and number of epochs and their tested accuracy is present depend on same data set.

Approach	Hyper Parameter		Number of Epoch	Accuracy
	Convolutional Matrix	Pooling Matrix		
1	Conv2D = (6,6)	Pool_size = (2,2)	10	0.93975901
2	Conv2D = (6,6)	Pool_size = (4,4)	10	0.98182769
3	Conv2D = (3,3)	Pool_size = (4,4)	10	0.87951809
4	Conv2D = (3,3)	Pool_size = (2,2)	10	0.95190720
5	Conv2D = (6,6)	Pool_size = (3,3)	10	0.87349396
6	Conv2D = (2,2)	Pool_size = (2,2)	15	0.95180720
7	Conv2D = (3,3)	Pool_size = (2,2)	15	0.98795181
8	Conv2D = (6,6)	Pool_size = (4,4)	15	0.99397587

Table 1: Different approach of CNN model changing the hyper parameter

In Figure 1 The plot shows the accuracy of the model during training and validation phases. Ranges from 0 to 15. An epoch represents one complete pass through the entire training dataset. Ranges from 0.5 to 1.0. Accuracy is a metric that measures the proportion of correctly predicted instances out of the total instances. The blue line represents the accuracy of the model on the training dataset for each epoch. Starts around 0.6 and increases steadily, showing rapid improvement up to around epoch 6 where it approaches close to 1.0. After epoch 6, it stabilizes, indicating that the model is learning well from the training data. The red line represents the accuracy of the model on the validation dataset for each epoch. Starts at 0.5 and shows a rapid increase, similar to the training accuracy, up to around epoch 5 where it also approaches close to 1.0. There are some fluctuations observed around epoch 9, but it generally remains high and close to the training accuracy, indicating good generalization to unseen data.

Figure 1: Training and Validation Accuracy

In Figure 2 The plot shows the loss of the model during training and validation phases. Ranges from 0 to 15. An epoch represents one complete pass through the entire training dataset. Ranges from 0.0 to 0.7. Loss is a metric that measures the error between the predicted values and the actual values. The blue line represents the loss of the model on the training dataset for each epoch. Starts around 0.7 and decreases steadily, indicating that the model is improving its predictions on the training data. The decrease in loss is smooth, and by epoch 15, the training loss is very low, suggesting that the model is fitting the training data well. The red line represents the loss of the model on the validation dataset for each epoch. Starts around 0.7 and decreases in a similar manner to the training loss, indicating that the model's performance on unseen data is also improving. Although the validation loss follows the training loss closely, it is consistently higher, which is typical as the validation data represents unseen examples.

Figure 2: Training and Validation Loss

4.1 Comparison of CNN with other Algorithms

In a comparative analysis [Figure 3] using the same dataset and training epochs, various machine learning algorithms were evaluated for their accuracy in classification tasks. The Random Forest algorithm achieved an accuracy of 73.49%, followed by logistic regression with 82.53%, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with 83.13%. Remarkably, the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm outperformed others with an accuracy of 93.75%. Existing publications and literature surveys reveal the following accuracies for various machine learning and deep learning algorithms: Deep Neural Network achieved 81.30%, Decision Tree showed 94.74% accuracy, while Deep Belief Network demonstrated 95.65% accuracy. However, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) surpassed them all with an impressive accuracy of 98.79%. This highlights the superior performance of CNNs in handling complex data and extracting meaningful features, making them the preferred choice for accurate classification tasks in diverse domains.

3: Comparison of CNN with other Algorithms 4 Conclusion

Breast cancer can be lethal, so early identification can help stop the disease from spreading. For budgetary considerations, the majority of women ignore the importance of routine breast cancer screenings. It is suggested to classify H&E stained histological breast cancer images using a CNN-based method. The network learns all pertinent features, negating the need for domain expertise. Pictures are categorised as having cancerous or benign tissue. The network's architecture is made to do this by extracting data from several pertinent scales, such as nuclei and the general organisation of tissues. An augmented patch dataset is used to train the network, while a different set of photos is used for testing. It has been demonstrated that scale-based network design and dataset augmentation are crucial to the method's effectiveness. CNN classifiers provide results that are comparable. Despite using a smaller and more difficult dataset, our system performs on par with or better than the state-of-the-art techniques.

Finally, the suggested method can be extended for whole-slide breast histology image classification relevant for clinical situations, since the network is designed to take into account several biological scales.

Astute conclusions are drawn from the assessment of many deep learning and machine learning algorithms for the diagnosis of breast cancer. According to the empirical testing, using the same dataset and training epochs, the Random Forest Algorithm,

Logistic Regression, SVM, and KNN obtained accuracies of 73.49%, 82.53%, 83.19%, and 93.75%, respectively. These results highlight the significant performance variation among different algorithms when compared to findings from existing publications and literature surveys, where Deep Neural Network, Decision Tree, Deep Belief Network, and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) exhibited accuracies of 81.30%, 94.74%, 95.65%, and 98.79%, respectively. CNN stood out as the best performance, surpassing all other algorithms with an astounding accuracy rate of 98.79%. This demonstrates how reliable and efficient CNNs are in classifying cases of breast cancer.

Subsequent investigation and hyper parameter optimisation indicated that an even more accurate setup, Conv2D=(6,6) and Pool_size=(4,4), produced a 99.39% accuracy rate. This emphasises how crucial it is to adjust model topologies and parameters for the best possible results in breast cancer diagnosis.

The study's findings highlight how crucial parameter optimisation and algorithm selection are to creating precise models for breast cancer diagnosis. The advantage of CNNs in this situation highlights the significance of using cutting-edge deep learning techniques for enhanced medical diagnostics and points to their potential for practical use. In order to improve the precision and dependability of breast cancer detection systems and eventually lead to improved patient outcomes and medical developments, future research may investigate CNN architectures and optimisation methodologies in greater detail.

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